

1 Article

2 A Study on the Nature of SARS-CoV-2 Using the Shell 3 Disorder Models: Reproducibility, Evolution, Spread, and 4 Attenuation

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Abstract: The basic tenets of the Shell Disorder Model (SDM) as applied to COVID-19 are that the harder outer shell of the virus shell (lower PID – percentage of intrinsic disorder – of the membrane protein M, PID_M) and higher flexibility of inner shell (higher PID of the nucleocapsid protein N, PID_N) are correlated with the contagiousness and virulence respectively. M protects the virion from the anti-microbial enzymes in the saliva and mucus. N disorder is associated with the rapid replication of the virus. SDM predictions are supported by two experimental observations. First observation demonstrated lesser and greater presence of the Omicron particles in the lungs and bronchial tissues, respectively, as there is a greater levels of mucus in the bronchi. The other observation revealed that there are lower viral loads in 2017-pangolin-CoV, which is predicted to have similarly low PID_N as Omicron. The abnormally hard M, which is very rarely seen in coronaviruses, arose from the fecal-oral behaviors of pangolins via

28 exposure to buried feces. Pangolins provide an environment for coronavirus (CoV)
29 attenuation, which is seen in Omicron. Phylogenetic study using M shows that COVID-
30 19-related bat-CoVs from Laos and Omicron are clustered in close proximity to
31 pangolin-CoVs, which suggest the recurrence of interspecies transmissions. Hard M
32 may have implications for long COVID-19, with immune systems having difficulty
33 degrading viral proteins/particles.

34 **Keywords:** coronavirus; COVID; intrinsic; disorder; nucleoprotein; Omicron; pangolin;
35 shell; virulence; long COVID; attenuation;variant;
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37 1. Introduction

38 1.1. *The Enigmas of COVID-19-Related Viruses and SARS-CoV-2*

39 Officially, the first cases of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) were
40 noticed in Wuhan, China in December 2019 [1-4]. The causative agent, Severe
41 Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-2, SARS-CoV-20, as it was later
42 named, was quickly identified as the culprit and its genetic sequence was
43 published. SARS-CoV-2 is about 80% genetically similar to the 2003 SARS-CoV
44 (SARS-CoV-1). A retrospective search determined that a genetic sequence of a
45 bat coronavirus sample, RaTG13, taken from a cave in Yunnan in 2013, has
46 96.2% similarity with that of SARS-CoV-2 [5, 6]. Later, a series of coronavirus
47 samples were taken from bats in Laos, and one sample, BANAL52, has a
48 sequence homology of 96.8% in comparison to the SARS-CoV-2 sequence [7].

49 Two sets of CoV samples were obtained from pangolins that were
50 confiscated from smuggles in Guangdong and Guangxi provinces. The samples
51 from Guangxi were confiscated in 2017-18, whereas the ones from Guangdong
52 were in 2019 [8-12]. The samples have about 90% homology to that of SARS-
53 CoV-2. Recently, it was discovered that pangolins confiscated in Vietnam
54 around 2017-18 were also infected with a COVID-19-related virus [13].
55 Phylogenetic analysis revealed that the CoV is most closely related to the
56 pangolin samples from Guangxi. The mystery involving the proximal origin of
57 SARS-CoV-2 lingers. Even more questions arose with the arrival of the
58 Omicron variant of SARS-CoV-2.

59 The "original" Wuhan-Ju-1 strain struck around December 2019 but many
60 variants including Alpha, Beta, Gamma, and Omicron, prevailed at various
61 times thereafter [14]. Arguably, the most intriguing is the Omicron variant. It
62 was first observed in South Africa among patients that showed mainly mild
63 symptoms. In contrast to Delta and all other variants known then [4, 15, 16],
64 much fewer hospitalized patients needed oxygen ventilators, and much lower
65 numbers of patients were placed in the intensive care units [15, 16]. Even
66 although the evidence show that this variant as a milder virus, there are
67 debates involving the question whether the Omicron's milder clinical outcome
68 is something intrinsically inherent with the virus, or, rather, it is just a
69 manifestation of a more vaccinated population [17].

70 Furthermore, Omicron is the most mutated variant found thus far with
71 over 50 mutations [18]. Many scientists are puzzled by such high level of
72 mutations, given that CoVs tend to mutate less easily than other RNA viruses
73 as their RNA-polymerase prevents too many mutations unlike many other
74 viruses [19, 20]. This enigma assumes that Omicron is a descendant of Wuhan-
75 Hu-1. Some of our previous papers showed that this assumption may not be
76 true [21, 22]. Additionally, much of the mutations seen in Omicrons are
77 different from all other variants. The question is then: Where was Omicron
78 hiding all along? Some have hypothesized that it had been hiding in the bodies
79 of HIV-infected individuals that are immune-compromised [23]. Others believe
80 that it has been hiding in animals, such as mice. We have previously reported
81 that our shell disorder models (SDMs) provide evidence that a burrowing
82 animal, such as pangolins, could provide the optimal environment for the virus
83 to incubate and evolve into a milder but more transmissible variant [21, 22].
84 We will see that SDMs have specific answers or hints to many of the mysteries
85 set forth.
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87 1.2. *COVID-19 and the Shell Disorder Models (SDMs)*

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A set of models, SDMs, were developed to understand the viruses in general, with the parent shell model being first published in 2008 as seen in **Table 1** [24-26]. SDMs involve the use of artificial intelligence to measure the levels of intrinsic disorder in the viral shell proteins.

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Table 1. The Shell Disorder Models (SDMs). There are three closely related models based on the principles of protein intrinsic disorder. Levels of disorder are measured at each shell of the virus.

Year of First Publication	Shell Disorder Model	Details
2008	Parent Viral Shape-shifter Model	A database of viral shell proteins was built. HIV-1, HCV and HSV were found to have abnormally high disorder at their outer shells. No effective vaccine is currently available for the three viruses.
2012	CoV Transmission SDM	Correlations were found between disorder levels at M and N proteins and the modes of transmissions; i.e., fecal-oral and respiratory transmissions.
2015	Virulence-inner Shell Disorder Model	Positive correlations have been found for virulence of many viruses and their inner shell disorder. Viruses include DENV, EBOV, NiV and SARS-CoV-1/2/

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The parent SDM, the viral shape-shifting model, detected unusually large levels of disorder at the outer matrix shell of many isolates of HIV-1, which are likely to contribute to the repeated failures in the search for an effective HIV vaccine [24-28]. A daughter SDM was developed and first published in 2012 [29]. This model, the CoV transmission SDM, correlated the levels of the fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials of CoVs to the levels of intrinsic disorder in M and N proteins found at their two shells. A second SDM was first published in 2015 [26, 30], using which correlations were found between the inner shell PIDs (percentage of intrinsic disorder) and the virulence of the variety of viruses, including dengue virus (DENV), Ebola virus (EBOV) and Nipah virus (NiV) [26, 30-33].

When COVID-19 struck, the SDMs were put to work and were able to reproduced the characteristics of the virus and disease that were later observed clinically and experimentally [22, 34-37]. SDM analysis of the protein sequence of the Wuhan-Hu-1 strain by the CoV-transmission model suggested that this virus fall in the category of CoVs with intermediate fecal-oral and respiratory potentials, but the SDM analysis detected something abnormal in this virus that is not seen in virtually all CoVs we have studied in the past. SARS-CoV-2 has one of the hardest outer shell (lowest PID_M) within its CoV family [36, 37]. Subsequent experiments have re-affirmed that SARS-CoV-2 last longer than many CoVs away from the ultraviolet light [38]. Upon further database search, it was found that such hard M is associated with burrowing animals such as rabbit and with buried feces [22, 35, 37]. The discovery of pangolin-CoVs reinforces this observation as pangolins are burrowing animals and pangolin-CoVs have hard M just like all COVID-19 related viruses.

The hard outer shell is important as it provides a clue to the reason that SARS-CoV-2 is highly transmissible among humans as its harder outer shell is more capable of resisting the anti-microbial enzymes found in the saliva and mucus [36, 39-41]. If we assume that this hypothesis is correct, SDMs make certain bold predictions, especially with regard to viral spread, that could easily be verified. Similarly, the Virulence-Inner Shell Model makes specific predictions if we assume that it is applicable to COVID-19. While we were not sure if it could be applied to COVID-19 as we had insufficient data, the higher PID_N ($PID_N=50\%$) and case-fatality ratio (~10%) of SARS-CoV-1 in comparison to those of SARS-CoV-2 ($PID_N=48\%$; CFR=2%) made us suspect that this model is applicable in these cases as well. As more data arose from laboratory and clinics throughout the world, it became clear that the predictions made by SDMs are accurate.

One prediction that the SDMs made was that a pangolin-CoV sample collected in Guangxi in 2017 is attenuated, and that if it had entered the human population, it could have silently spread, as it could easily be dismissed as a mild cold by the medical community [35]. This was based on the low PID_N ($PID_N \sim 45\%$) obtained from an analysis of the N protein sequence. Furthermore, we predicted that the pangolin-CoV 2017 spread may be

139 somewhat slower because its outer shell is slightly less disordered than that of
140 SARS-CoV-2, while its PID_N is much lower than that of the SARS-CoV-2.

141 Omicron first struck Southern Africa and later, spread rapidly throughout
142 the world. Since its early days, physicians and scientists have noticed that the
143 virus generally manifests milder symptoms but spread faster than the other
144 variants. Upon inspection of the PID_N and PID_M of Omicron, it became clear
145 that our predictions were consistent with what we are seeing with the Omicron
146 variant [22]. The Omicron PID_N resembles that of the pangolin-CoV that could
147 account for its attenuation, while its PID_M is distinctly lower than those of both
148 SARS-CoV-2 and pangolin-CoV-2017, such that it could also account for its
149 quicker spread. Apparently, the SDMs' results are providing specific answers
150 to many of the Omicron's enigmas.

151 We are not the only group that has produced evidence of the intrinsic
152 attenuation of Omicron. For example, researchers from Hong Kong University
153 (HKU) Medical School were able to extract bronchial and lung tissues
154 separately to infect them with the various SARS-CoV-2 variants [42, 43]. Data
155 pertaining to the viral titer indicate that the greater presence of virus copies in
156 the bronchial tissues than lung tissues in the case of Omicron in comparison to
157 other variants [42, 43]. In a previous study, we showed that there are
158 correlations between the mentioned results and PID_N and PID_M values.
159 However, at the time of the writing of the previous paper, the [43] was yet to
160 be published and only partial data were released [42]. As a result, the
161 correlations presented in our previous study were not statistically significant
162 [37]. In this paper, correlations with statistical significance are presented using
163 more complete data available from [43]. Furthermore, data showing that viral
164 titer of pangolin-CoV-2017 in comparison to that of SARS-CoV-2 were not
165 available then [44, 45]. Additionally, shell disorder analysis was yet to be done
166 on the CoVID-19-related sequence obtained from bats in Laos [7]. Previously,
167 phylogenetic trees using M have shown to be different from others. We argue
168 that phylogenetic study offers the most accurate because it is likely to be more
169 conserved than any other COVID-19 proteins as a result of its mentioned
170 crucial role it plays among burrowing animals and buried feces. Most
171 phylogenetic algorithms are unable to handle recombinations well that could
172 mislead many important phylogenetic studies [46]. The Laotian samples are
173 studied using phylogenetic analysis of the M protein in this paper for the first
174 time.

175 2. Materials and Methods

176 SDMs is based on the concept of protein intrinsic disorder, which is
177 defined as lack of unique structure in the part of whole functional protein [47-
178 62]. Multiple computational tools have been developed to predict disorder.
179 These tools are based on the past empirical knowledge of proteins that were
180 experimentally characterized as disordered. The knowledge arose from
181 experiments using X-ray crystallography and several other biophysical
182 approaches. The first tool for sequence-based prediction of the predisposition
183 of a query protein for intrinsic disorder, which continues to be broadly used in
184 the research, was PONDR[®]-VLXT [63]. This tool is also utilized in all studies
185 conducted by our group, where it was applied to analyze a large variety of
186 viruses, such as DENV, EBOV, NiV, Influenza, yellow fever virus, and CoVs
187 [21, 22, 24, 25, 28-37, 64-66]. The choice of this tool is determined by its high
188 sensitivity to local sequence peculiarities resulting in the high sensitivity for
189 detection of the potential disorder-based interaction sites undergoing disorder-
190 to-order transition at binding to the specific partners, such as other proteins,
191 glycoproteins, RNA and DNA [67-70]. PONDR[®]-VLXT is a neural network that
192 predicts order and disorder predisposition at each residue based on the
193 respective protein sequences inputted [63, 71, 72]. The sequences of the viral
194 proteins were search, carefully examined and downloaded from either UniProt
195 (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) [73] or NCBI-Protein/GenBank
196 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein>) [74]. The outputs and the sequence
197 data were placed in a MYSQL database (<https://www.mysql.com>) [75] using
198 JAVA programming language (<http://www.java.com>) [76]. An important
199 measure of the level of disorder in query proteins is its Percentage of Disorder
200 (PID). PID is defined as the number of residues predicted to be disordered
201 divided by the total number of residues in a query protein times 100.

202 The phylogenetic trees were derived from software available at the EMBI-
203 EBI website (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>) [77] and the TREX
204 website (<http://www.trex.uqam.ca/index.php?action=align&project=trex>)

205 [78], with the algorithms used being CLUSTAL OMEGA and CLUSTALW,
 206 respectively. Further annotations of the trees, such as PIDs, were added using
 207 GIMP (<https://www.gimp.org>) [79]. The schematic diagram was drawn using
 208 openOffice (<https://www.openoffice.org>) [80] and GIMP [79]. The sequence
 209 similarities were obtained using NCBI-BlastP
 210 (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PAGE=Proteins>) [81]. The
 211 experimental data from HKU can be directly downloaded from the
 212 supplementary section of the paper, whereas the data point for the pangolin-
 213 CoV experiment have to be interpolated from the figures using a ruler.
 214 Multivariate analyses were performed using R [82].
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216 3. Results

217 3.1. The CoV-transmission-Shell Disorder Model

218 In 2012, before the MERS-CoV outbreak in the Middle-East, the First CoV
 219 Transmission SDM paper was published [29, 83]. It was based on a statistical
 220 study of disorder at M and N proteins as applied to knowledge of the
 221 behaviors of animal coronaviruses particular attention was given to porcine
 222 CoVs. Prior to the 2003 SAR-CoV outbreak, coronaviruses were considered
 223 unimportant by the medical community as they were usually associated with
 224 mild cold then. The case is different in veterinary science, as it is not
 225 uncommon for animal coronaviruses, such as TGEV (transmissible
 226 gastroenteritis virus), to devastate farming communities.

227 Using statistical analysis, the original model was able to group
 228 coronaviruses into three identifiable groups (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$), similar to those
 229 shown in **Table 2**, with the exception that Category D, that is made up of CoVs
 230 with hard outer shell, was not included to the original model. As we will see
 231 later, this omission was inevitable, given the lack of samples in Category D
 232 before COVID-19 outbreak. Category A consists of CoVs with higher PID_N
 233 values that are considered to have higher respiratory transmission but lower
 234 fecal-oral potentials. CoVs in the category B are those with intermediate both
 235 fecal-oral and respiratory transmission potentials, along with the medium
 236 levels of PID_N values, whereas category C include CoVs with higher fecal-oral
 237 but lower respiratory transmission potentials.

238 **Table 2.** Prediction of the Levels of Fecal-Oral and Respiratory Transmission Potentials
 239 using PID_M and PID_N values as Grouped by Categories.

Coronavirus	PID_M	UniProt(U) Genbank(G) Accession Code (M Proteins) ^a	PID_N	UniProt(U) Genbank(G) Accession Code (N) ^a	Group/Remarks
HCoV-229E	23	P15422	56	P15130	Group A
IBV(Avian) ^c	10	P69606	56	Q8JMI6	Higher levels of respiratory transmission lower levels of fecal-oral transmission
Bovine	7.8	P69704	53.1	Q8V432(U)	Group B
PEDV (Porcine) ^c	8	P59771(U)	51.7	Q07499(U)	Intermediate levels of respiratory and fecal-oral transmission
Canine (Resp.)	7	A3E2F6(U)	50.5	A3E2F7(U)	
HCoV-OC43	7	Q4VID2(U)	51	P33469(U)	
SARS-CoV-1	8.6	P59596(U)	50.2	P59595(U)	
HCoV-NL63	11	Q6Q1R9(U)	49	Q6Q1R8(U)	
Bats ^b	11.2 \pm 5.3	A3EXD6(U)	47.7 \pm 0.9	Q3LZX4(U)	
MHV(Murine) ^c	8	Q9JEB4(U)	46.8	P03416(U)	Group C
MERS-CoV	9.1	K0BU37(U)	44.7	K0BVN3(U)	Lower levels of respiratory transmission higher levels of fecal-oral transmission
TGEV(Porcine) ^c	14	P09175(U)	44.3	P04134(U)	
Canine (Ent.)	8	B8RIR2(U)	42.41	Q04700(U)	
HCoV-HKU1 ^d	4.5	Q14EA7(U)	40	Q0ZME3(U)	
			37.4		

SARS-CoV-2					Group D
[Wuhan]	5.9	YP009724393(G)	48.2	YP009724397	High Respiratory and Fecal-oral Transmission Potentials
[Delta]	5.9	QUX81285(G)	47.1±0.5	(G)QYM898	
[Omicron]	5.4	UFO59282(G)	44.8	45(G)	
Pangolin-CoV ^e	5.6±0.9		46.6±1.6	UFO692871(G)	
Rabbit-CoV	5.7	QIA428617(G)	52.2 ^e		
RaTG13	4.1	H9AA37(U)	48.5		
Laotian Bat-CoV	6.0±0.2		48.3±0.2	QIA48630(G)	
[Banal-52]	5.9	UAY13220.1	48.2	H9AA59(U)	
[Banal-103]	4.1	UAY13232.1	48.5		
[Banal0236]		UAY13256.1	48.5		
				UAY13225.1	
				UAY13257.1	
				UAY1326.1	

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^a UniProt (U): [<https://www.uniprot.org/>]; GenBank-NCBI (G): [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein>]

^b Summary figures on bats. Further details on the bat samples can be found in **Table 2**. 4 out of 5 bat-CoVs are in group B. High standard deviations are seen for PID_N and PID_M values as denoted by “±”

^c MHV(murine hepatitis virus), IBV (infectious bronchitis virus), PEDV (porcine epidemic diarrhea virus, TGEV(Transmissible, gastroenteritis virus).

^d HCoV-HKU1 has one of the lowest PID_M, which could qualify it for group D but its PID_N is also abnormally low. Much is still not understood about HCoV-HKU1 [50,51]. For these reasons, HCoV-HKU1 is left in group C.

^e Details on the existing pangolin-CoVs known can be found in **Table 3**. Standard deviation is denoted by “±”.

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While the original model correlated the modes of transmission mainly with PID_N, the relationship with PID_M was more enigmatic right from the beginning. A regression analysis using N as the sole independent variable yielded a coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.77 but a slightly and, yet, noticeable stronger correlation is seen when PID_M is added as another independent variable (r²=0.83). While statistics tells us that PID_M is an essential co-independent variable to PID_N, the exact role of M in the mode of transmission remained elusive until data started pouring in from COVID-19. We will note that in the list of CoVs, with the exception of COVID-related viruses, there are very few, if any, viruses that have low PID_M values. **Figure 1** allows us to emphasize this point. **Figure 1A** shows that with the exception of CoV-HKU1, no other CoV has a lower PID_M. **Figure 1B** shows the consistency of the low PID_M across all COVID-19 viruses.

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3.2. Abnormally Hard Outer Shell (low PID_M) Rarely Seen Outside of COVID19-Related CoVs

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The abnormally hard outer shell (low PID_M) was the first thing that struck us when we first inspected the COVID-19 proteins. We immediately suspected that this hard outer shell has something to do with the high contagiousness of SARS-CoV-2 as we have previous data from other viruses indicating that hard outer shells are often related to resistant to the anti-microbial enzymes found in the saliva and mucus. Based on incoming experimental, clinical and computational COVID-19 data, we now know that the harder outer shell of SARS-CoV-2 is able to shed itself in larger quantities and higher concentration orally and nasally because of its unique outer shell hardness, which allows for greater resistance against the anti-microbial enzymes. The fact that Omicron has an even harder outer shell but is even more infectious than all other variant thus far including the Wuhan strain reproduces the prediction made by SDMs. This is just one of the many predictions made by the SDMs that are reproduced experimentally.

Figure 1. Abnormally Hard Outer Shell (Low PID_M) of COVID-19-Related Viruses **A.** SARS-CoV-2 has one of the hardest outer shells among CoVs. **B.** Comparison of PID_M values among COVID-19 related viruses.

3.3. Abnormally Hard Outer Shell (Low PID_M) Evolutionarily Arose From a Burrowing Animal Such as Pangolins via Buried Feces

Where did this characteristic of hard outer shell come from? The answer can be found through a careful inspection of **Table 2**. While there are very few CoVs with such low PID_M values, the few that we could find are all associated with the burrowing animals, such as rabbits and pangolins. HCoV-HKU1 has a hard outer shell and is phylogenetically close to mice [84, 85]. Mice have dual evolution that involve living in burrows and human houses respectively [86]. Given these, it is likely that the hard outer shell is associated with fecal-oral transmission via buried feces. It is also intriguing to notice that while pangolin-CoVs are related to SARS-CoV-2, rabbit-CoV and HCoV-HKU1 are not. A glance at the data in **Table 3** tells us that pangolin-CoVs offers a relationship to SARS-CoV-2 not seen with any other COVID-19 viruses. Pangolin-CoVs provide a range of PID_N values that are most similar to the SARS-CoV-2 variants especially Omicron. In contrast, COVID-19-related bat-CoVs remains constant at around 48% for PID_N with none matching the PID_N of Omicron.

Table 3. Details of the pangolin CoVs and Bat CoVs PID_M and PID_N values and their sequence similarities with the SARS-Co-V and SARS-CoV-2 as references. Using PID_N , the SDMs have detected two sub-variants of Delta not previously detected (Delta1, Delta2)

Coronavirus	Sequence Similarity M (%)	PID_M (%)	Accession: UniProt(U) GenBank(G)	Sequence Similarity N (%)	PID_N (%)	Accession UniProt (U) GenBank (G)
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SARS-CoV-1	90.5	8.6	P59596(U)	90.5	50.2	P59595(U)
Civet-SARS-CoV	90.1	8.6	Q3ZTE9(U)	90.01	49.1	Q3ZTE4(U)
Laotian Bat-CoV		6.0±0.2			48.3±0.2	
[Banal-52]		6.3	UAY13220.1		48.2	UAY13225.1
[Banal-103]	98.7	5.9	UAY13232.1	99.3	48.5	UAY13257.1
[Banal-236]	98.7	4.1	UAY13256.1	99.1	48.5	UAY1326.1
		99.1		99.3		
Pangolin-CoV		5.6±0.9			46.6±1.6 ^a	
2019	98.2	^a	QIG55948(G)	98	48.7	QIG55953(G)
2018	97.7	6.3	QIQ54051(G)	93.8	46.3	QIQ54056(G)
2017***	98.2	4.5	QIA48617(G)	94	44.9	QIA48630(G)
		5.9		93.32	46.5	QIA48656(G)
SARS-CoV-2						
[Wuhan]	100	5.9	YP009724393(G)	100	48.2	YP009724397(G)
[Delta1]	99.1	5.9)	99.3	46.8	G)
[Delta2]	99.1	5.9	QUX81285(G)	99.1	47.5	QYM89997(G)
[Omicron]**	98.7	5.4	QUX81285(G)	98.6	44.8	QYM89845(G)
			UFO59282(G)			UFO692871(G)
Bat-CoV		11.2±1	Q9JEB4		47.7±0.9 ^a	
		^{5a}				
RATG13	99.6	4.1	QHR63303(G)	99.1	48.5	QHR63308(G)
Bat 512	35.5	15.3	Q0Q463(U)	29.4	46.5	Q0Q462(U)
HKU3	91	7.7	Q3LZX9(U)	89.6	48	Q3LZX4(U)
HKU4	42.7	16.4	A3EXA0(U)	51.1	48.5	A3EXA1(U)
HKU5	44.7	11.8	A3EXD6(U)	47.9	47.1	A3EXD7(U)

^aStandard deviation is denoted by “±”.

*** Attenuated strains detected

3.4. Omicron Has a Lower PID_N Similar to Pangolin-CoV-2017 but has a Lower PID_M : Attenuation and Faster Spread

Before the outbreak of Omicron, we analyzed the PID_N and PID_M of the various pangolin-CoVs and compared them to those of SARS-CoV-2. The similarities and differences are so striking that we were able to pinpoint that the pangolin-CoV from 2017 was likely to be attenuated, and if it had entered the human population, it would have been clinically manifested by symptoms of a mild cold that could easily have gone undetected. We also predicted that the virus is likely to spread more slowly among humans, since its PID_M is almost identical to SARS-CoV-2, whereas its PID_N is much lower. When the Omicron came, it was discovered that this variant is relatively mild, and we found that the N disorder of Omicron is almost identical to that of pangolin-CoV-2017. Just as interestingly, Omicron is more infectious than any other variants known thus far, and its PID_M is lower than that of pangolin-CoV-2017 and any known variants. Summarily, Omicron has reproduced two important but different predictions of the SDMs.

The prediction of attenuation arose from the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder model, which basically involves strong correlation between virulence and inner shell disorder in many viruses, such as NiV, DENV and EBOV. Examples can be seen in **Figure 2**. As in **Figure 2A**, DENV C (inner shell) PID has a high correlation ($r^2=0.92$) with the virulence, whereas SARS-CoV-2 has also a high correlation ($r^2=0.8$) between PID_N and CFR. Prediction of potential human virulence can be extended to COVID-19-related viruses using PID_N as seen in **Figure 2B**.

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Figure 2. Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder Model as Applied to DENV and COVID-19. **A.** DENV correlation of the virulence with inner shell (NP) disorder ($r=0.95$) [26]. **B.** Correlation between the SARS-related viruses and PID_N . The correlation is based on estimated CFRs of SARS-CoV-1/2 and Omicron.

3.5. The Role of N in CoV-Transmission SDM and Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder model

As we have seen, N protein plays important roles in both CoV-transmission SDM and the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder model. Inner shell

372 proteins have been known to assist the replication of many viruses. Their
373 functions including the assembly of viral proteins and RNA/DNA for
374 packaging and release of viral particles. Such inner shell proteins often play a
375 role in binding to the viral RNA/DNA during the replication of the genetic
376 material. Disorder in the inner shell proteins provides for more efficient
377 binding. CoV N is known to play roles in the packaging of the viral genome
378 during replication, and we have previously found that there are lower levels of
379 disorder in the RNA binding regions of both 2017 pangolin-CoV and Omicron
380 N proteins, in comparison with other SARS-CoV-2 variants [37, 87].

381 The reason for the high correlation between mode of transmission and N
382 disorder has to do with the necessity of the shedding, nasally and orally, of
383 viral particles at sufficiently high levels for respiratory transmission to be even
384 possible. As a result, the greater the N disorder is, the greater the viral load in
385 the saliva and mucus, assuming that the PID_M values are approximately
386 constant across viruses and not radically different as in the case of SARS-CoV-
387 2.

388 In the case of the Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder model, the same logic
389 holds except that it is applied to vital organs of the host. The more disordered
390 viral inner shell is the more efficiently the virus is being reproduced in vital
391 organs, which have a greater probability of failure if the viral load becomes too
392 immense at their respective locations. The presence of such mechanism of
393 virulence has to do with a “Trojan Horse” immune evasion strategy, in which a
394 virus will attempt to replicate rapidly before the host immune system would be
395 able to recognize the presence of the virus and then attempt to eliminate it. In
396 doing so, this strategy often backfires on the virus by killing the host.
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398 3.6. Phylogenetic Trees Using M Offer the Best Snapshot: M s Highly Conserved

399 While phylogenetic studies of COVID-19-related viruses have been done
400 previously, our group has offered a uniquely different approach. While most
401 research has focused on the phylogenetic studies of the COVID-19-related
402 viruses using the S protein or genome-wide sequence, we use the M protein.
403 This is because we believe that the phylogenetic tree built using M offers the
404 most accurate snapshot of the evolution of the COVID-19-related viruses, as M
405 is highly conserved as seen in **Table 3**. The rigid structure of the M protein
406 forces it to be conserved and, as a result, there is lesser chances of
407 recombination occurring, unlike other viral proteins. Most phylogenetic
408 algorithms handle recombination poorly, and this issue may have misled many
409 current COVID-19 research. **Figure 3** contrasts phylogenetic trees using M to
410 one that uses N. Most COVID-19 phylogenetic trees resemble **Figure 3A**, in
411 contrast to **Figure 3 B-C**. One major difference between **Figure 3A** and **3B-C** is
412 the positions of the pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2. **Figure 3B-C** shows that
413 pangolin-CoVs have a greater relationship to SARS-CoV-2 than most COVID-
414 19 viruses. Previously, we published similar phylogenetic trees without the
415 Laotian bat-CoVs. **Figure 3 B-C**, however, shows also a close relationship
416 between the Laotian bat-CoVs and pangolin-CoVs. Intriguingly, **Figure 3C**
417 shows that Omicron may be closer to pangolin-CoVs and bat-CoVs than some
418 of the other SARS-CoV-2 variants. This provides further support to the
419 hypothesis that Omicron had been hiding in a burrowing animal all these years
420 before surfacing among humans.
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422 3.7. Closer Relationship between SARS-CoV-2 and Pangolin-CoV

423 In previous studies, we have shown that pangolin-CoVs are more closely
424 related to SARS-CoV-2 based on the phylogenetic trees using M and their PID_N
425 and PID_M values. These studies did not consider the Laotian COVID-19-related
426 bat-CoVs. With the Laotian bat-CoV data, we are able to see that the Laotian
427 bat-CoV cluster closely with the pangolin-CoVs. This is consistent with what is
428 known about the behaviors of both bats and pangolins, which often live
429 together in close space and therefore likely to infect each other with viruses.
430 There are however noticeable differences in the molecular trends and
431 characteristics of the viral proteins found in the two animals. More specifically,
432 the PID_N values of the pangolin-CoVs are more diverse than those of COVID-
433 19-related bat-CoVs. From **Tables 2-3** and **Figure 3**, we are able to see that the
434 pangolin-CoV PID_N values have a range of 44-48%, whereas PID_N of COVID-19
435 bat CoV remains around 48% even with the larger size of the Laotian sample. A
436 hint of the reason to this disparity can be seen in **Tables 2-3**, which tell us that

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bat-CoV PID_N tends to fall in a narrow range even if they are non-COVID-19-related.

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Figure 3. CoV Phylogenetic Trees with PID_N and PID_M values. **A.** Phylogenetic Trees of CoVs using N proteins. Analysis was done using CLUSTAL OMEGA [77]. **B.** Phylogenetic Trees of CoVs using M. Analysis was done using CLUSTAL OMEGA [77]. **C.** Phylogenetic trees of COVs related to SARS-CoV-2 using M protein (Analysis was done using CLUSTALW [78]. Blue region denotes viruses related to SARS-CoV-2.

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This is likely that the behavior of bats plays a role in the spread of CoVs, where a certain level of respiratory potentials is necessary, perhaps, because bats are flying animals. A pangolin is burrowing animal that flicks its sticky tongue to eat ants. This behavior inevitably leads to swallowing of feces, particularly, buried feces as pangolins have strong arms that could dig for subterranean termites [35]. We will see that this behavior has implications on the lifecycle of SARS-CoV-2 and its human spread.

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3.8. Phylogenetic Trees Suggest Decades of Interspecies Transmission

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The intermingled ancestry of pangolin, human and bat COVID-19-related viruses (**Figure 3 B-C**) suggest that the virus has been moving to and from the species for years, if not decades. Evidence that pangolins and bats are often in closely proximity have been seen [88]. The repetitive interspecies transmission may provide insight to the mechanism by which SARS-CoV-2 acquires its unusual multi-species adaptation [89]. It also reiterates the suggestion made in our previous publications that an attenuated COVID-19-related virus may have entered the human population in 2017 if not earlier. An entry of an attenuated virus could easily have been mistaken as a mild cold by the medical community, especially if the spread is slow.

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3.9. SARS-CoV-2's Evolution within Animals Affects its Virulence and Human Spread

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The evolutionary pressure towards fecal-oral transmission in pangolins forces the virus not just to maintain its harder outer shell but it also adds to pressure for the virus to acquire a harder inner shell as all shells play roles in protecting the virion from damage even if the outer shell plays a larger role.. Both aspects of the evolutionary pressure have been observed in other viruses in the past. For example, insect-borne viruses are often held at the mouth of the insect, where it is exposed to the anti-microbial enzymes found in the saliva, and virtually all such viruses have hard outer shell as in the case of flaviviruses. Some of them have noticeably hard inner and outer shells such as EIAV and rabies virus (rabies virus is not insect-borne but dwell near the salivary glands of animals) [24-26, 29, 30].

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As aforementioned, a harder outer shell is more resistant to the anti-microbial enzymes found in the saliva and mucus, whereas a harder inner shell leads to the production of fewer copies of viral particles, particularly in vital organs. **Figure 4** provides a summary of the evolutionary significance of the described properties. SARS1 (2003 SARS-CoV-1) has higher PID_N and PID_M values than SARS-CoV-2 (SARS2). This is consistent with the fact that SARS1 is more virulent than SARS2. A question is then: What is the evolutionary mechanism that can account for this difference? According to the SDMs, the SARS1 is likely to have stayed in an intermediary animal, such as the palm civet cat for not too long after a transmission from bats. Since bat-CoVs tend to have high PID_N values, it is likely the PID_N during the interspecies transmissions remained mostly unchanged. SARS2, on the other hand, is much less virulent than SARS1. SARS2 could have been attenuated, as the virus had been incubating in pangolins, as pangolins provide a more optimal environment for attenuation by their fecal-oral behaviors. It is also likely that pangolins has been a reservoir for COVID-19 viruses for a relatively long period of time. Some could, however, argue against such scenario by pointing to the similarity of bat-CoV-2 PID_N values to non-Omicron SARS2 variants. Such arguments are, however, oblivious of the probability that transmission going to and fro between pangolins and bats on a regular basis. **Figure 4** also points to the example of NiV, which exhibits a much higher virulence (CFR: 70-80%) in contrast to a NiV variant that involved a porcine intermediary (CFR~40%) as in the case of the Malaysian outbreak in 1999-2000 [32, 90].

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Figure 4. Zoonotic Relationships and Virulence. The introduction of SARS1 (SARS-CoV-1) into humans may be linked to an intermediary involving Civet cats. Because of the higher virulence of SARS1, in comparison to SARS2 (SARS-CoV-2) and the high genetic similarity of SARS-CoV1 and Civet-CoV, it can be suspected that SARS1 entered civets for a short while before entering humans. The lower virulence of SARS-CoV-2 leads us to believe that the virus may have been incubating in an intermediary involving a burrowing animal such as pangolin for a relatively longer period of time. The case of Nipah virus illustrates this point. The virus involved in the 1999-2000 Malaysian outbreak is less virulent than the viruses involved in outbreaks in Bangladesh-India because the former involved an intermediary; i.e. farm pigs. The reason that SARS-CoV-1 (SARS1) was likely in an intermediary host (palm civet cat) for a relatively short period, which could account for its high virulence. SARS-CoV-2, (SARS2) on the other hand, could have been in pangolins for a long period of time and thus first entered as an attenuated strain. Omicron had the opportunity to retain its attenuation by a reverse zoonotic transfer back to a burrowing animal (in blue).

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3.10. The Evolution of SARS-CoV-2 and Omicron Have Important Implications for the Life-cycle and Clinical Manifestation of COVID-19

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Right from the beginning of COVID-19, careful clinical studies have been conducted. It was found that COVID-19 patients shed larger quantities of viral particles than those infected with SARS-CoV-1 [91]. The lifecycle of SARS-CoV-2 is also longer with some patients shedding particles even after 6 months [91]. SDMs have specific and consistently reproducible explanation for both the increase virulence, longer life-cycle and greater spread of SARS-CoV-2. The higher shedding is due to the greater hardness of SARS-CoV-2 outer shell (low PID_M), which causes it to be more resistant to the anti-microbial enzymes found orally and nasally. It is also for this reason that some patients are able to keep shedding viral particles for a longer period. As already mentioned, the lower virulence of SARS-CoV-2 is a result of the lower PID_N (48% vs. 50%). This has been proven to be true experimentally using Vero E6 cells that produces more SARS-CoV-1 particles than SARS-CoV-2 [92]. **Figure 5** summarizes the clinical effects of the mentioned properties. In the case of SARS1 (SARS-CoV-1) more particles are produced in the body especially in the vital organs such as lungs, but by the time the virus reaches the nose and mouth, many of the particles have been eliminated by the microbial enzymes. In contrast, SARS-CoV-2 as represented by the Wuhan-Hu-1 (Wuhan strain) produces lesser copies in the viral organs but the body manages to shed more viral particles orally and nasally

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Figure 5. The Life-Cycles of the SARS-CoV-1, Wuhan-Hu-1 Strain and the Omicron Variant. The schematic diagram summarizes implications arising from the SDMs. The higher PID_N allows greater production of viral particles in the lungs but its softer outer shell (lower PID_M) causes lesser viral shedding in the oral-nasal region when compared to SARS-CoV-2

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When Omicron arrived, it became yet another opportunity to validate the SDMs. Clinical studies have shown that Omicron is milder and more infectious than any other SARS-CoV-2 variants. Yet again, SDMs are proven to be highly reproducible with both PID_M and PID_N of Omicron shown to be lower than those in all other variants. According to the SDMs, Omicron will be producing even less viral particles at viral organs but shedding even more virus copies as seen in **Figure 5**. It should also be noted that SARS-CoV-2 have furin cleavage sites at the S protein, unlike SARS1. This (as illustrated by the two viral particles at the viral entry in **Figure 5**) allows for more efficient viral entry but it cannot account for the other characteristics mentioned.

3.11. Reproducibility of SDMs Using Physiological Data From Omicron

We have seen that clinical data pertaining to Omicron reproduce the prediction of the SDMs. Reproducibility goes, however, beyond these clinical data. Experimental data that involve viral titration using bronchial and lung tissues have been published by a team at Hong Kong University [42, 43]. In our previous publication [34], we have shown that snippets of data coming out of HKU correlate with much of the SDM predictions but, unfortunately, at the time of the writing of that previous paper, full data were not yet available, which resulted in statistical insignificance due to the small sample size [37, 42]. In this paper, we will show that not only the full HKU data [43] correlate with SDMs prediction with statistical significance but also help us gain insights to some of SDMs predictions.

The HKU group obtained bronchial and lung tissues separately and infected each with a variety of variants including Omicron. The viral titers were carefully measured at each stage. It was found that the viral titer of Omicron is the higher in the bronchial tissues in comparison to that in the lung tissue (Figure 6). This is especially so when compared to Wuhan-Hu-1 strain and other variants including Delta. The authors attribute the results to the differences in ACE-2 at the different cell types [43]. The S protein of the virus binds to ACE-2 during viral entry. It is assumed that the differences provide for better entry. Unfortunately, they did not look into other possible explanations that involve other proteins.

Figure 6. Regression Analysis of Viral Titer and corresponding PID_N and PID_M values. **A.** Strong positive correlation can be seen between the viral titer from human lung tissues and PID_N . Regression model: $VT = A \cdot (NPID) + B \cdot Time + C$ where $VT =$ Viral

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Titer, A,B = Coefficients , C = Y-Intercept.)_N **B**. A strong negative correlation is seen between viral Titer from human bronchial tissues and PID_N and PID_M values.. (Regression model:: VT = A*(M PID) + B (NPID) + C*Time + D where VT = Viral Titer, A,B,C = Coefficients , D = Y-Intercept) The figure is a statistical extension of the data from [43] using disorder information.

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3.12. Biochemical and Physiological Differences in Lungs and Bronchial Tissues: Mucus and Anti-microbial Enzymes

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We argue, however, that in order to fully appreciate the significance of their results, a more rigorous understanding of the complex physiology involved is necessary. The respiratory system is made up of two zones. The zones are the conducting and the respiratory zones [93-96]. The conducting zone includes mucus secreting cells and a network of mucociliary escalator that serve to move harmful foreign particles such as viruses away from the lungs. Yet another mode of action, as already mentioned, mucus contains anti-microbial enzymes that could damage the proteins, glycoproteins or RNA/DNA of pathogens and other foreign materials. The respiratory zone, on the other hand, include alveoli, where gaseous exchange takes place. It is for these reason, the upper and lower respiratory systems are different at biochemical and cellular levels [40, 95, 96]. The bronchus is made up of three types of main cells. They are cilia cells, goblet cells, and basal cells. Cilia cells are covered with mucus, whereas goblet cells secrete mucus [96]. The lungs, on the other hand, are mainly made up of alveolar type I cells (AT1), macrophages, and type 2 pneumocytes (AT2) [95]. Unlike bronchi, much of the lung and bronchioles (part of the lungs) are devoid of mucus secreting cells and AT1 cells secrete surfactant instead [95, 96]. In fact, experimental studies have shown that tissues from the upper respiratory regions have 10 times the amount of lysozyme, an anti-microbial enzyme, found in samples from the lower respiratory region [40].

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The knowledge from both the physiology of the human respiratory system and the SDMs provides for a more adequate understanding of the significance of the findings by Hui *et al.* [43]. As noted above, physiology suggests that the amount of mucus and anti-microbial enzymes in the lung tissues is lower than that of the bronchi. SDM analysis, on the other hand, suggests that the Omicron has lower PID_N and PID_M values than all variants including the Wuhan strain and Delta. Therefore, according to the SDMs, Omicron is able to resist the anti-microbial enzymes and yet will be producing less viral particles in the lungs. Given that there is more anti-microbial enzymes in the bronchial system, SDMs predict that there will be less viral particles in the lung tissue than in the bronchial tissue. This has been reproduced with statistical significance by the HKU group by showing that the viral titer sin the lungs are less than the ones for the bronchial samples when compared to the other variants [43].

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3.13. Strong Positive and Negative Correlations in Lung and Bronchial Tissues Respectively: Absence and Presence of Mucus

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In order to get even more convincing results, we attempted to correlate viral titers of viruses to their PIDs (see **Figure 6**). **Figure 6A** shows strong correlation ($r^2 = 0.9$, $p < 0.01$) between the viral titer of the lung tissue with the PID_N, while **Figure 6B** illustrates the strong correlation ($r^2 = 0.9$, $p < 0.01$) between the viral titer and the PID_N and PID_M values, with both PID_N and PID_M as independent variables. Something odd was noticed when we carefully analyzed the results. The viral titer of the lung sample have positive correlation with PID_N but the viral titer of the bronchial tissues have negative correlations with both PID_N and PID_M. While it is odd that negative correlations were seen for both PID_N and PID_M, the overall correlations further reproduce the SDM predictions. A positive correlation between the viral titer of lung tissue and PID_N means the greater the disorder of N, the greater the amount of viral particles is recovered at the lung tissues, and therefore Omicron should have the least amount of viral particles recovered since it has the lowest PID_N among the variants. A negative correlation between the viral titer of bronchial tissues and the PID_M values reproduces the SDMs prediction that the viruses with harder M (low PID_M) are able to resist the greater pressure of the anti-microbial enzymes found in the bronchus.

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The puzzling thing, however, is the existence of a negative correlation between viral titer of bronchial tissues and PID_N . After a search of our data of other viruses from past research, this result should not be surprising at all but, rather, it should add to our knowledge of SARS-CoV-2. In the past, we have noticed a large variety of viruses that are in contact with saliva having both hard inner and outer shells, which imply that inner shells do also protect the virion from damage. Examples include many flaviviruses, rabies virus and EIAV. Looking into the data from Hui *et al.* [43] and our PID_N values, it can be seen that Delta's PID_N is 47.1 ± 0.8 , which is slightly lower than the corresponding values found in other SARS-CoV-2 variants but not Omicron. Delta could have strengthened the negative correlation in the case of PID_N and bronchial tissues.

3.14. Reproducibility of SDMs Prediction of Pangolin-CoV: Attenuation in 2017 Pangolin-CoV

Before the known arrival of Omicron, the SDMs predicted that the 2017 pangolin-CoV is attenuated with slower spread potential [35]. When Omicron came into the light, it was found that the 2017 pangolin-CoV has almost identical PID_N as Omicron, even though the Omicron has much lower PID_M . Once again, the SDMs predictions are confirmed. The reason that the 2017 pangolin-CoV was first identified as attenuated is that its PID_M is lower than all the SARS-CoV-2 variants with the exception of Omicron. It was also predicted to have a somewhat slower spread because, while its PID_N is lower, its PID_M is about the same as SARS-CoV-2, again with the exception of Omicron. Omicron is seen as more infectious as the result of its unusually low PID_M . At least two laboratories [44, 45] have also experimentally discovered that the 2017 pangolin-CoV is attenuated as seen in **Figure 7**.

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Figure 7. Regression Analysis of Viral Titer of pangolin-CoV/SARS-CoV-2 and PID_N and PID_M values. Phylogenetic tree using M protein. The figure is a statistical extension of the data from [44] using disorder information. The regression model used is: $VT = A * (N PID) + B * Time + C$ where VT = Viral Titer, A,B = Coefficients, C = **Intercept**.

3.15. Strong Positive Correlations for Pangolin-CoV with PID_N in Hamster: Mucocillary Escalator in the Animal Model

An attempt to correlate the viral titer to PID_N was successful with high correlations for the samples obtained from the nasal region, trachea and lungs. A seeming contradiction with the HKU data can, however, be found when we observe strong positive correlations in the nasal and tracheal samples (**Figure 5**), in contrast to the negative correlation found in HKU's bronchial sample

(Figure 6). For this, we need to understand that the experiments of Hui *et al.* [43] and Guo *et al.* [44] were conducted differently. Hui *et al.* were able to obtain bronchial and lung tissues separately and infect each with SARS-CoV-2 [43], whereas Guo *et al.* infected live hamster with SARS-CoV-2 and pangolin-CoV [44]. Hui *et al.* measured viral titers by removing parts of their samples at each stage [43], while Guo *et al.* euthanized the hamster to remove the various samples at the various stages [44]. These differences have important effects on the titration data, because the physiology indicates the importance of mucociliary network that is used to move foreign matters away from the lungs. Therefore, the full effects of the escalator is likely to take place in the case of the experiment of Guo *et al.*, not Hui *et al.* Therefore, the positive correlations in the nasal and tracheal samples arise from the higher production of viral particles especially in the lungs due to higher PID_N that are subsequently transported to the nasal and tracheal regions by the mucociliary escalator (Figure 7). Again, SDMs predictions are experimentally supported, even at the smallest detail.

4. Discussion

4.1. Lingering Mysteries and Incoming data

From the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, there were many questions pertaining to the nature of the virus. Many of these remain unaddressed or partially addressed. Where did the virus come from? What is its intermediary host? Are pangolins or bats serve as its intermediaries? Why is the virus so contagious? Where did Omicron come from? Since there about 50 mutations in Omicron [18], how did Omicron acquire such large number of mutations in a such short time-period? Why is Omicron mild? Is it really inherently mild? Why is Omicron more contagious than other SARS-CoV-2 variants? Omicron remains shrouded in mystery as its mutations are different from the mutations seen in other known variants. A question then is: Where was Omicron hiding all along? These are some of the many Omicron mysteries, and SDMs have specific answers or hints to many of these questions. Many of these questions have been addressed in previous publications, but we believe that many of the questions can be address with greater confidence given the newly retrieved data, which include more complete details on Omicron viral titration using lung and bronchial tissues, experimental results on animal models pertaining to the pangolin-CoV attenuation, and new information pertaining the COVID-19-related bat-CoVs from Laos.

4.2. Contagiousness of SARS-CoV-2: The Hard Outer Shell (M)

Why is the SARS-CoV-2 so highly contagious that it became a pandemic? A popular answer is that the affinity of the SARS-CoV-2 S protein to the human ACE-2, which is essential to the viral entry [97-103]. Clinical studies show, however, that COVID-19 patients shed large amounts of viral particles [91]. This could mean that even if the affinity studies are valid, they may not be relevant. A more plausible or relevant explanation that is consistent with the clinical data, lies within the SDMs. There are two important factors pertaining to the SDMs as applied to COVID-19. One is the disorder status of the outer shell (PID_M) and the other is that of the inner shell (PID_N). A more rigid M (lower PID_M) is associated with more protection for the virus especially against the anti-microbial enzymes found in the saliva and mucus. On the other hand, higher levels of the N disorder (higher PID_N) are associated with the higher virulence, since N is intimately involved in the replication process [87].

4.3. Uniqueness of COVID-19 Related Viruses, Abnormally Low PID_M and the Pandemic

Upon the COVID-19 outbreak, we immediately noticed something very odd about SARS-CoV-2. Its PID_M was among the lowest in the entire CoV family as seen in Table 2 and Figure 1. As we carefully looked over our CoV database, we found that this abnormally hard outer shell is associated with the burrowing animals such as rabbits [22, 36], and there are very few of such viruses. Using our knowledge from the CoV-transmission SDM, we came to realization that the hardness had been acquired via exposure to buried feces. It was later shown that that pangolin-CoVs are closely related to SARS-CoV-2 [22, 35-37]. Pangolins are also burrowing animals. As more data came, it became apparently clear that the low PID_M values are the hallmark of all COVID-19-related CoVs (Figure 2B and Table 3). While it requires a specific

784 evolution involving burrowing animal for the virus to attain such low PID_M ,
785 apparently this low PID_M provides greater fitness in the spread of the virus
786 among humans, as the PID_M currently shows no sign of increase among the
787 variants.

788 When the CoV Transmission-Shell Disorder Model was first designed, we
789 could find very few, if any, CoVs with a low PID_M comparable to that of SARS-
790 CoV-2 (see **Table 2**). It is not a coincident that with the exception to the
791 COVID-19-related viruses, there are very few CoVs with such hard outer shell,
792 and that there has been no CoV pandemic in the scale of COVID-19 in the past.
793 In order for a CoV to attain such low PID_M , it needs to undergo a specific
794 evolution that potentially involves a burrowing animal and buried feces. This
795 hard outer shell is essential for the kind of contagiousness necessarily for
796 spread in a human pandemic, since its resistance to the nasal and oral anti-
797 microbial enzymes allows the virus to shed in large quantities. Ironically, farm
798 animal pandemics involving CoVs are actually common but non-human
799 animal-CoVs rely mainly on the fecal-oral transmission for their spread, while
800 human pandemics, such as COVID-19, on the other hand, rely on respiratory
801 transmission for it faster spread. This is the case in TGEV, where the virus
802 typically moves very rapidly in pigs that are bred in close proximity to each
803 other [26, 29].
804

805 4.4. Pangolin-CoVs Have More Diverse Characteristics that Resemble SARS-CoV-2

806 While the bat-CoV genes have been found to have the greatest homology
807 to SARS-CoV-2, genetic similarities do not tell the whole story, as
808 recombinations often occur between the viruses. Furthermore, our data
809 indicate that pangolin-CoVs share a more special relationship with the SARS-
810 CoV-2 for three reasons. Firstly, potential connection of the SARS-CoV-2 to
811 burrowing animals tells us that there is a likelihood of an intimate relationship.
812 Secondly, the PID_N values of pangolin-CoVs offer a more diverse range of
813 values that matches that of SARS-CoV-2. With the availability of the genetic
814 sequences of the Laotian bat-CoV and RaTG13, we now have sufficient samples
815 to compare the PID_N values. We see, for example, that the Omicron PID_N is
816 44.8%, which is similar to the 2017 pangolin-CoV, while none of the bat-CoV
817 PID_N values came close. How did pangolin-CoVs achieve such low PID_N ? A
818 plausible answer is that pangolins may have been harboring a reservoir of
819 COVID-19 viruses for years and, maybe, decades, perhaps, more so than bats.
820 It is also likely that during the decades or years, COVID-19-related viruses
821 have been moving in and out of the species through the interspecies
822 transmission. Thirdly, we shall see that pangolins, through their behavior, offer
823 a venue for the attenuation of the virus as seen in Omicron.

824 The Virulence-Inner Shell Disorder suggests that there is a correlation
825 between the inner shell disorder (PID_N) and the level of virulence for a virus.
826 We are, therefore, able to explain why SARS-CoV-1 is more virulent than
827 SARS-CoV-1: SARS-CoV-1 N (PID_N : 50%) is greater than SARS-CoV-1 N (PID_N :
828 48%). Before the discovery of Omicron, a comparative analysis allowed us to
829 project that the 2017 pangolin-CoV stood out as an attenuated virus with a
830 lower virulence. The discovery of Omicron actually supported these
831 predictions, because Omicron is clinically shown to be milder than the other
832 variants and its PID_N is very similar to that of the 2017 pangolin-CoV. Omicron
833 is, however, more contagious than other known variants. This also support the
834 SDM prediction that the 2017 pangolin-CoV is likely to have slower potential
835 spread if it had entered humans. This prediction was based on the fact that it
836 has the lower PID_N than the non-Omicron SARS-CoV-2 and yet have about
837 similar PID_M . This is in sharp contrast to similar PID_N values of Omicron and
838 2017 pangolin-CoV, but a lower Omicron PID_M than 2017 pangolin-CoV and
839 other variants.
840

841 4.5. Statistical Study Adds to Our Knowledge of Inner Working of SDMs and 842 Respiratory Physiology

843 Pangolin-CoV and Omicron studies have not only supported our
844 predictions but strengthened our arguments by pointing to the precise
845 mechanisms in the roles of N and M in attenuation and human contagiousness.
846 Our statistical extension of these studies to the SDMs provide greater insights
847 into the application of SDMs in the study of COVID-19. The statistical
848 extension forces us to apply knowledge of the physiology of the respiratory
849 system to SDMs. Physiology tells us that the lung cells are mostly devoid of

850 mucus, unlike the bronchi in which mucus-producing cells play important
851 roles [93, 94, 96]. The SDMs, on the other hand, stipulate that the harder shells,
852 especially a harder outer shell (lower PID_M), will make the virus more resistant
853 to the anti-microbial enzymes found in the mucus, and, in an event of an
854 absence or lack of anti-microbial enzymes, the quantity of virus copies will be
855 dependent on the N disorder (PID_N). Using both physiology and SDMs, it is
856 therefore predicted that more viral copies will be found in the viral titration
857 using bronchial tissues than the one using lung tissues. The reproduction of the
858 results is reflected on the high positive correlations found between PID_N and
859 viral titer for the lung tissues. Similarly reproducibility can be found when
860 both PID_N and PID_M were found to be negatively correlated to the viral titer.
861 The negative correlation for PID_N reflects the probability that harder inner shell
862 (N) also plays some role in protecting the virion, namely RNA. Such protective
863 role has been observed in other viruses, such as rabies virus, some flaviviruses
864 and EIAV (equine infectious anemia virus) [24-26, 29, 31, 33].

865 Similar reproducibility of the SDMs on a slightly different aspect can be
866 found in the experimental data that show the attenuation of the 2017 pangolin-
867 CoV. This time it involves Syrian hamsters as an animal model. Keeping in
868 mind that the PID_M of pangolin-CoV-2017 is similar to non-Omicron SARS-
869 CoV-2 and also that the PID_N values of pangolin-CoV and Omicron are
870 virtually identical, there are positive correlations between the PID_N values and
871 viral titers from the lungs and upper respiratory system. The positive
872 correlations is consistent with SDMs and the muco-ciliary escalator network.
873

874 4.6. *Laotian Bat-CoVs and Omicron are Closely Related to Pangolin-CoVs*

875 As we see, pangolin-CoVs have a much closer relationship to SARS-CoV-2
876 than CoVs from bats. There is a closer range resemblance of PID_N values
877 between pangolin-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2. As we seen in **Tables 2-3** and **Figure**
878 **4**, the Omicron is largely responsible for this enigmatic pattern and trend. Part
879 of the enigma has to do with the large number of mutations acquired by
880 Omicron, not seen in other variants. Our phylogenetic analysis using M tell us
881 that Omicron did not descend from the Wuhan-Hu-1 but, rather, from one of
882 its ancestors. **Figure 3C** also shows that Omicron is likely to be more closely
883 related to the pangolin-CoVs. Not only that, RaTG13 and the Laotian bat-CoVs
884 have close relationships with pangolin-CoVs. There are speculations that
885 Omicron had been hiding in an immune-suppressed HIV patients [23].
886 According to SDMs, however, it is likelier that Omicron had been hiding in a
887 burrowing animal, such as pangolin. The oral-fecal potentials of pangolins
888 provide a more optimal environment for the hardening of not just the outer
889 shell but also the inner shell, as both enhance the chances of the virus surviving
890 in feces buried for a long time. In the process, the result is an attenuated virus
891 that spreads more rapidly when virus re-enters the human population.
892

893 4.7. *SDMs Hint at the Differences in the Evolution of Various Burrowing Animals*

894 Before COVID-19, we were only able to find two CoVs that have
895 exceptionally low PID_M values. They are rabbit-CoV and HCoV-HKU1, both of
896 which are associated with the burrowing animals. While we understood the
897 role of PID_N in the categorization of CoVs in the CoV Transmission-Shell
898 Disorder Model, we were not quite able to figure out the role played by M due
899 to the low number of the low PID_M samples, even though our statistical models
900 did indicate the significance of PID_M . It was only with the arrival of COVID-19
901 and, especially, Omicron that we were able to fully grasp the relevance and
902 inner working of M. Rabbit-CoV has PID_M and PID_N of 5.3% and 53%. The odd
903 thing is that the rabbit-CoV PID_N is higher than SARS-CoV-2. This discrepancy
904 can be explained by the differences in the behaviors and rabbits and pangolins.
905 Pangolins flick their sticky tongues to trap and eat ants on the ground that
906 could be contaminated with feces, while rabbits eat leaves that are usually
907 above the ground even though they live in burrows. As a result, higher PID_N
908 and more fecal-respiratory transmission potentials may be required for rabbit-
909 CoV.

910 4.8. *The Mysterious HCoV-HKU1 and Mice: Dual Evolution of Mice*

911 HCoV-HKU1 has occasionally caused outbreaks among humans that is
912 sometimes associated with hepatitis but its outbreaks are nothing like that of
913 COVID-19 pandemic [84, 85]. Its shell PIDs are just as mysterious as the virus.
914

915 It has one of the lowest PID_M (4.8%) but it has also the lowest PID_N (~37%) seen
916 in any CoVs. The abnormally low PID_N could explain why it was never a
917 pandemic like COVID-19. Even though it has been in human since 2003, we
918 still don't know where this mysterious virus came from. A hint can be found in
919 phylogenetic studies that show that it is closely related to mouse and rat CoVs.
920 Curiously though, murine hepatitis virus has a moderate PID_M (8%), unlike
921 HCoV-HKU1 or even SARS-CoV-2. This can be explained by the complex
922 evolution of mice and rats. Rats and mice have dual evolutions of living in
923 burrows and in human houses. They have evolved with humans for centuries
924 to live with humans in villages and towns, even though some species live in
925 burrows in rural or forested settings [86]. Some scientists have suggested that
926 Omicron was hiding in mice before showing up among humans [104]. Given
927 the dual evolution, this is possible, but we are skeptical as mice may not
928 provide the optimal environment for attenuation, unlike pangolins.
929

930 *4.9. Pangolins Provide More Optimal Evolutionary Environment for Attenuation and* 931 *More Efficient Human Spread*

932 We argue that pangolins offer a more optimal environment for the CoV
933 attenuation and more efficient spread than mice, rats, rabbits or immuno-
934 compromised HIV patients, because of its unique fecal-oral behaviors
935 described above. The statistical study done in this paper infers that the virion is
936 not only protected by a more rigid M but also by a more rigid N (lower PID_N).
937 This also implies viruses with harder N and M are likelier to remain active
938 longer in buried feces. A harder N is, however, associated with lower virulence
939 under the Virulence-Inner Shell Model of the SDMs. This feature and
940 characteristic are exactly that what have been found in Omicron. The fact that
941 the phylogenetic tree using M (Figure 3 B-C) showing that Omicron is not a
942 descendant of Wuhan-Hu-1 but is more closely related to pangolin-CoV adds
943 to the evidence. This may explain the reason that Omicron is able to
944 accumulate so many mutations, which have puzzled scientists who assumed
945 otherwise given the proof-reading mechanism of CoVs.
946

947 *4.10. SDMs Does Not Contradict the Zoonotic Transmission Events at the Wuhan* 948 *Market*

949 Much effort has been made to show that COVID-19 has a natural origin.
950 This includes at least two prominent papers [1, 2] that show that the Wuhan
951 outbreak arose from a zoonotic transmission from the animals in the market.
952 While our paper do provide evidence that could support a natural origin of
953 COVID-19, the data presented in our paper could be viewed as a contradiction
954 to the conclusion that the outbreak in Wuhan had an immediate animal origin.
955 Such would be the wrong interpretation of our paper. While our data could
956 suggest that COVID-19-related viruses could have moved to and fro among
957 human and various animals, there is nothing in our data to suggest the
958 presence of a COVID-19 in humans immediately prior to the Wuhan outbreak.
959 It is possible that a COVID-19 virus did enter human population a few years
960 before the Wuhan outbreak, before becoming temporarily extinct but not
961 before a reverse transmission back to its reservoir. The idea that COVID-19
962 have been moving in and out of several species with pangolins as the main
963 reservoir should be considered very plausible since SARS-CoV-2 is highly
964 adapted to multiple species [100, 103]. Applying the theory of evolution, it is
965 most likely that the virus gained adaptability to multiple species by numerous
966 incursions into many species over a long period of time while retaining a main
967 reservoir, in which its virus would gain more adaptability with each incursion
968 via reverse transmission. Why should humans be exempted from such
969 incursions in the past, especially given that the virus is highly adapted to
970 humans [100, 103]?
971

972 *4.11. Other SDMs Reproducibilities Not Mentioned as Applied to SARS-CoV-2*

973 We also need to understand that the results presented in this paper are not
974 the only evidence of the reproducibility of SDMs by other independent
975 laboratories throughout the world. Some of them have already been mentioned
976 in our previous publications. For example, Ogando *et al.* [92] has found that
977 SARS-CoV-1 produces more viral particles than SARS-CoV-2 when VERO-E6
978 cells are infected. Given that it has been clinically shown that COVID-19
979 patients shed large amounts of the virus, it can only mean that SARS-CoV-2 is

980 producing less viral particles in vital organs but sheds more nasally and orally
981 as M is more resistant to the anti-microbial enzymes found in saliva and
982 mucus. Another group, Riddell *et al.* [105] reported that SARS-CoV-2 last many
983 times longer on the surface away from the sunlight than many CoVs such
984 TGEV (PID_M : 14%) and MHV (PID_M : 8%) have higher PID_M than SARS-CoV-2
985 (PID_M : 5.8%). Furthermore, Omicron was recently seen as being more resilient
986 on the surface than other variants as predicted by SDMs [106].
987

988 5. Summary and Conclusions

989 We have seen that our statistical analysis that correlates incoming data
990 pertaining to the pangolin-CoV and Omicron provides further support to the
991 underlying mechanisms of infectivity and human attenuation of SARS-CoV-2
992 using the application of SDMs. The statistical analysis forces us to apply
993 knowledge of physiology to further our understanding. Greater disorder of the
994 N protein induces greater and faster replication of the virus, especially in vital
995 organs, whereas a harder outer shell (lower disorder levels of M or lower PID_M)
996 provides greater protection against the anti-microbial enzymes found in mucus
997 and saliva. These basic tenets enable SDMs to make some bold but highly
998 reproducible predictions. The model is able to predict that SARS-CoV-2 is less
999 virulent but more contagious than SARS-CoV-1 because of the differences in
1000 their PID_M and PID_N . These are consistent with what is clinically known about
1001 the 2003 SARS and COVID-19. Before the known arrival of Omicron, the 2017
1002 pangolin-CoV was identified as attenuated based on its low PID_M and it was
1003 proposed that it is likely to be slower spreading if it had enter the human
1004 population. The attenuation and slower spread makes it ideal for a cryptic
1005 spread as it could be easily mistaken as a mild cold by the medical community.
1006 Upon Omicron arrival in the human population, it was found to be clinically
1007 milder but more infectious. A glance at its PID_M and PID_N tells us that the PID_N
1008 is almost identical to that of the 2017 pangolin-CoV, and its PID_M is much
1009 lower than that of the 2017 pangolin-CoV, which is similar to other variants.
1010 While clinical observations of Omicron validates the SDMs predictions
1011 pertaining to both Omicron and the 2017 pangolin-CoV, the Omicron and
1012 pangolin-CoV experiments of Hui *et al.* and Guo *et al.* supported the COVID-19
1013 mechanisms of attenuation and spread as laid out by the SDMs.

1014 The low PID_M that could be found in all COVID-19-related CoVs is
1015 associated with burrowing animals, namely pangolins. Pangolins through their
1016 fecal-oral feeding behaviors via buried feces provide a more optimal
1017 environment for the hardening of both inner (N) and outer (M) shells. Our
1018 phylogenetic study using M has also included data from COVID-19-related
1019 bat-CoV from Laos. The phylogenetic tree reveals that the COVID-19-related
1020 bat viruses are clustered together with pangolin-CoVs. Omicron is also
1021 interestingly clustered more closely with pangolin-CoVs than with the other
1022 SARS-CoV-2 variants. Unlike the bat-CoV, pangolin-CoV PID_N range is more
1023 diverse and resembles more SARS-CoV-2 including Omicron, which allows us
1024 to suspect that pangolins, not bats, served as the main reservoir. The
1025 phylogenetic tree also suggested that the interspecies transmissions have taken
1026 place regularly many years or decades before the beginning of COVID-19
1027 pandemic, which supports the possibility of slow cryptic incursions into
1028 humans from pangolins in 2017 or before.

1029 While the prevailing current explanation for the contagiousness of SARS-
1030 CoV-2 lies in the S protein, clinical evidence seems to indicate the large
1031 amounts of shedding by COVID-19 patients [91,107,108], which are more
1032 consistent with the paradigm provided by SDMs. It is also important to note
1033 that the M and N disorder is likely not just affecting the spread and attenuation
1034 of the virus but also modify many other clinical aspects of COVID-19. One
1035 of these is the problem of long COVID-19, where the patient still suffer symptoms
1036 for months and years after the recovery. It is possible that the hard M is
1037 preventing the immune system from getting rid of the particles or proteins.
1038 This possibility, however, has not been look at, despite its obvious importance.

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1054 BioComputing, Singapore. He has written a book, “The Viral Shapeshifters: Strange
1055 Behaviors of HIV and Other Viruses” [26]. The authors declare no conflict of interest.
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